

Mechanistic Exploration of Parkinson's Disease by Integrating Co-expression Networks with AOPs

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Abstract

Understanding the mechanistic underpinnings of Parkinson's disease (PD) requires bridging molecular data with systems-level toxicological knowledge. We developed a prototype workflow that integrates Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) of in vitro transcriptomic datasets from dopaminergic neurons with mechanistic data from Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) resources.

Using WGCNA, we identified co-expression modules, highlighting network perturbations associated with neurodegeneration. These modules were then mapped onto AOP molecular initiating events and key events curated from AOP-Wiki using the AOP-explorer online tool.

The resulting integrated framework enables mechanistic visualization of gene clusters within the AOP context, linking transcriptomic signatures to established neurotoxic outcomes. This tool aims to support hypothesis generation, mechanistic anchoring of omics data, causal inference and the design of New Approach Methodologies for neurotoxicity testing and Parkinson's disease modeling.